

Survey of insects and diseases in Asia

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In a 1975 IRRI survey, 35 rice breeders at 28 research centers in 10 Asian nations were asked to rank, in order of severity, the four most serious insects and diseases that limit farmers' rice yields within the area served by each experiment station. The project was conducted in collaboration with Iowa State University, USA, and was partially funded by The Rockefeller Foundation.

The rice stem borer was most widely considered a serious pest. In 60% of 35 regions, its severity rating was 1.6, one of the highest, on a scale where 1 = most serious pest and 4 = fourth most serious. But when severity rating was calculated only for the stations where the stem borer was one of the four most serious problems, it rated fourth highest, 2.7 (see table). That may indicate that although the stem borer limits yields across vast regions, other local pests are usually more serious in individual areas.

Bacterial blight disease, with an overall severity rating of 1.6, was considered a major problem in 57% of the regions. Where bacterial blight was serious, it

Rice breeders' perceptions of the specific insect and disease pests that most seriously limit rice production in farmers' fields within the areas served by their research centers. Thirty-five rice breeders at 28 agricultural experiment stations and universities in 10 Asian nations, 1975.

Pest	Mean severity rating ^a		Breeders (%) who rated pest as one of 4 major constraints
	All stations	Stations where pest is a problem	
Stem borer	1.6	2.7	60
Bacterial blight	1.6	2.8	57
Brown planthopper	1.1	2.5	46
Blast disease	1.4	3.2	43
Gall midge	1.1	3.0	37
Tungro virus	0.7	2.3	29
Sheath blight	0.3	2.0	17
Green leafhopper	0.2	2.0	9
Helminthosporium	0.1	1.3	9
Striped virus ^b	0.3	3.0	9
Grassy stunt virus	0.1	1.0	6
Sheath rot	0.1	2.0	6
Other insects ^c	0.7	2.1	34
Other diseases ^d	0.4	2.1	20

^aOn a scale of 1-4: 4 = most serious insect or disease pest; 1 = fourth most serious. Calculated for all 35 areas and for only those regions in which each factor was considered one of four major pests.

^bOnly in Korea.

^cIncludes one rating each for whitebacked planthopper, leaf roller, paddy bug, seedling fly, stink bug, armyworm, gandhi bug, and two unspecified insects.

^dIncludes one rating each for bacterial leaf streak, black smut, sheath virus, glume blotch, stem rot, and two unspecified diseases.

received a rating of 2.8 — higher than that for the stem borer. The brown planthopper was a major pest in 46% of the regions. Its overall severity rating was 1.1 ; but in regions where it was a problem, it was rated 2.5. The fourth

most common of the serious Pests was blast disease, cited in 43% of the regions. It received an overall severity rating of 1.4, but at stations where it was a major problem, it had the highest rating, 3.2.

GENETIC EVALUATION & UTILIZATION

Insect resistance

IR26 found susceptible to the brown planthopper in North Sumatra, Indonesia

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The brown planthopper (BPH) has severely attacked rice in North Sumatra since about 1970. IR26 was first grown from 5 kg of seed brought to N. Sumatra from IRRI in 1974. Seedlings were transplanted near Tebingtinggi on 15 May 1974 and 3 t were harvested. By the end of March 1975 (the following season), IR26 was grown on about 67 ha; about 200 t were harvested. IR26 was planted on about 860 ha in the 1975–76wet

Empty areas where IR34 was hopperburned during early growth stages.